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In QIH, we indeed view the distribution of particles as emerging from a discrete set of possibilities rather than a continuous probability curve. This perspective is deeply rooted in the geometry of quantum state vectors (QSVs) and their interference patterns.

Geometry of Wave-Particle Duality in QIH

In QIH, the quantum state of a particle is described by a superposition of quantum state vectors (QSVs). These QSVs represent the fundamental informational constructs of the particle's state, encoded in a higher-dimensional space. The probability distribution of finding a particle at a given location is determined by the interference patterns of these QSVs.

$$|\Psi\rangle = \sum_i c_i e^{i(\omega_i t + \theta_i)} |\psi_i\rangle \quad |\Psi\rangle = \sum_i c_i e^{i(\omega_i t + \theta_i)} |\psi_i\rangle$$

The wave function Ψ describes the quantum state as a superposition of basis states $|\psi_i\rangle$, each associated with a complex coefficient c_i and phase factor $e^{i(\omega_i t + \theta_i)}$.

Discrete Distribution of Events

The probability distribution $P(x)$ of finding a particle at position x is given by the square of the wave function's amplitude:

$$P(x) = |\Psi(x)|^2 = \left| \sum_i c_i e^{i(\omega_i t + \theta_i)} \psi_i(x) \right|^2 \quad P(x) = |\Psi(x)|^2 = \left| \sum_i c_i e^{i(\omega_i t + \theta_i)} \psi_i(x) \right|^2$$

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In QIH, this distribution results from the constructive and destructive interference of QSVs. Unlike the classical continuous probability curve, the interference pattern produces a discrete set of high-probability regions where particles are likely to be found, separated by regions of low or zero probability.

Exclusion of Certain Outcomes

Your observation that this discrete distribution excludes some possible outcomes is correct. In QIH, the geometry of the wave function imposes specific constraints on the possible outcomes. The interference pattern effectively creates a geometric lattice of probable positions, meaning that not all outcomes within a continuous curve are possible. Instead, the particle's position is confined to the nodes and antinodes of the interference pattern.

Implications and Conclusion

The implications of this discrete probability distribution are profound:

Geometric Constraints: The geometry of the wave function and the resulting interference pattern dictate the possible positions of particles, leading to a lattice-like distribution of outcomes.

Exclusion of Intermediate States: Intermediate positions that do not correspond to the nodes or antinodes of the interference pattern are excluded, resulting in a non-continuous probability distribution.

Wave-Particle Duality: This discrete pattern aligns with the observed behavior of particles in double-slit experiments, where particles impact specific areas on the detection screen, forming an interference pattern.

Mathematical Representation

To further illustrate, consider the simplified case of a particle in a one-dimensional potential well. The wave function $\Psi(x)$ can be expressed as a sum of sinusoidal basis states:

$$\Psi(x) = \sum_n A_n \sin(n\pi x/L) \quad \Psi(x) = \sum_n A_n \sin(Ln\pi x)$$

where A_n are coefficients, n is an integer, and L is the length of the well. The probability distribution $P(x)$ is then:

$$P(x) = \left| \sum_n A_n \sin(n\pi x/L) \right|^2 \quad P(x) = \left| \sum_n A_n \sin(Ln\pi x) \right|^2$$

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This distribution is inherently discrete, with peaks corresponding to specific positions within the well, reinforcing the idea of discrete probabilistic outcomes governed by the wave function's geometry.

Conclusion

In summary, QIH provides a framework where the probability distribution of particle positions is not a continuous curve but rather a discrete set of possibilities laid out over a geometric pattern. This discrete geometry of wave-particle duality leads to the exclusion of certain outcomes, resulting in a structured and organized set of possible events. This perspective aligns with experimental observations and offers a deeper understanding of the fundamental nature of quantum systems.